

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxalic Acid Catalysed Oxidation of Nitrous Acid by Vanadium(V)**

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The kinetics and mechanism of the oxalic acid catalysed oxidation of nitrous acid by vanadium(V) have been studied in 1 M perchloric acid medium. The reaction is first order each in vanadium(V) and nitrite and fractional order in oxalic acid. Nitrate ion retards the rate of the reaction. At low $[H^+]$ (0.5–1.2 M) the rate of the reaction is independent of $[H^+]$ but at higher concentrations, the rate decreases. Kinetic as well as spectrophotometric evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between vanadium(V) and oxalic acid has been obtained and a mechanism involving this complex has been proposed.

RECENTLY we have reported¹ the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of nitrous acid by vanadium(V). Since oxalic acid is known to catalyse many vanadium(V) oxidations²⁻⁵, we have investigated the catalytic effect of oxalic acid in this reaction, the results of which are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Reagents: 0.25 M solution of oxalic acid was prepared by dissolving oxalic acid (BDH, AR) in distilled water.

An approximately 0.2 M stock solution of sodium vanadate was prepared from ammonium vanadate (Riedel) and sodium carbonate (BDH, AR) and standardised by the method of Gopala Rao and co-workers⁶.

0.5 M nitrite solution was prepared by dissolving sodium nitrite (BDH, AR) in 500 ml of boiled distilled water and standardised⁷.

0.1 M solution of vanadium(IV) was prepared by electrolytic reduction of vanadium(V) in 1 M perchloric acid and standardised⁸. 'Pro Analysis' grade perchloric acid (70%) supplied by E. Merck (India) and sodium perchlorate prepared by neutralisation of this acid with sodium carbonate (BDH, AR) were used.

Apparatus: A Shimadzu UV-VIS Double Beam spectrophotometer (140-02) with 1 cm silica cells was used for absorbance measurements. Lab constant temperature liquid circulatory bath S-36 (SEW-India) was used as the thermostat.

Stoichiometry of the reaction: Aliquots of nitrous acid were mixed with a known excess of vanadium(V) and oxalic acid in 1 M perchloric acid medium. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and the absorbance of unreacted vana-

dium(V) determined at 320 nm. After applying correction for blank the stoichiometry of the reaction was found to correspond to $2VO_2^+ + HNO_2 + 2H^+ \rightarrow 2VO^{2+} + HNO_3 + H_2O$

Kinetics procedure: The course of the reaction was followed by monitoring the absorbance of the unreacted vanadium(V) at 320 nm. At this wave length vanadium(V) has considerable absorbance while vanadium(IV) and nitrate have negligible absorbances. Since nitrite ion and oxalic acid have small absorbances at this wave length, the kinetic runs were monitored against a blank consisting of the same concentration of nitrite, oxalic acid and perchloric acid. Although the absorbance of vanadium(V) was found to increase with increase in oxalic acid, Beer's law was found to be obeyed at different [oxalic acid].

All kinetic runs were carried out at a constant temperature of $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless otherwise mentioned. The activity coefficients were controlled by maintaining a constant ionic strength with $NaClO_4$. Requisite amounts of perchloric acid and oxalic acid were taken in a jena glass reaction bottle and placed in a thermostat. Vanadium(V) and sodium nitrite were also thermostated separately. After the solutions had attained the temperature of the thermostat, the reaction was initiated by transferring calculated amounts of vanadium(V) and sodium nitrite in that order. The rate measurements were made isolating vanadium(V) by keeping nitrite in a ten fold molar excess compared to [vanadium(V)]. When $\log(\text{absorbance})$ was plotted against time, a straight line was obtained even upto 80% completion of the reaction indicating the reaction to be first order in vanadium(V). The rate constant of the catalysed part of the reaction, k_c , is obtained by subtracting the rate constant of the uncatalysed reaction, k_u , from the observed pseudo-first order rate constant, k_t .

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Results and Discussion

Effect of products : Of the two products, vanadium(IV) was found not to have any effect on the rate of the reaction, but the other, i.e. nitrate, was found to retard the reaction considerably. Since the plots of log (absorbance) vs time were found to deviate from linearity in presence of nitrate, initial rate method was employed to determine the rate of the reaction. The rates thus determined are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [NITRATE] ON THE INITIAL RATE

$[\text{NO}_3^-] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
I.R. $\times 10^4$, mol lit ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	2.13	2.03	1.97	1.76	1.68	1.63

In the absence of added nitrate, the reaction was found to follow pseudo first order behaviour upto 80% completion of the reaction. All other studies were, therefore, carried out in absence of added nitrate.

Effect of ionic strength : The rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in ionic strength. The plot of log k_c vs ionic strength was observed to be a straight line, indicating that the rate determining step probably involves a neutral molecule and an ion.

Order with respect to vanadium(V) : Kinetic runs were carried out at different concentrations of vanadium(V) keeping the concentrations of nitrite, oxalic acid and perchloric acid constant. Plots of log (absorbance) vs time were found to be parallel to one another, indicating the order with respect to vanadium(V) to be unity.

Order with respect to nitrite : To determine the order with respect to nitrite, kinetic runs were carried out at varying concentrations of nitrite, keeping the concentrations of vanadium(V), oxalic acid and perchloric acid constant. The plot of k_c vs [nitrite] was found to be a straight line passing through origin showing first order dependence of rate on [nitrite].

Order with respect to oxalic acid : Increase in [oxalic acid] was found to increase the rate of the reaction. The plot of log k_c vs log [oxalic acid] was found to be a straight line with a slope of 0.65 showing that the order with respect to oxalic acid is fractional. Further, the plot of $1/k_c$ vs $1/[\text{oxalic acid}]$ was found to be a neat straight line with an intercept on the rate axis (Fig. 1), thereby furnishing kinetic evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between vanadium(V) and oxalic acid.

Effect of hydrogen ion : Variation of $[\text{H}^+]$ was carried out from 0.5-2.0 M at constant ionic strength of 2.0 M (NaClO_4) and the data obtained are presented in Table 2. It may be seen from Table 2 that at low concentrations (0.5-1.2 M) H^+ has no effect on the rate, but at higher concentrations the rate decreases with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$.

Fig. 1. Michaelis-Menton plot.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\text{H}^+]$ ON k_c

$[\text{H}^+]$, M	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.5	2.0
$k_c \times 10^4$, sec ⁻¹	8.44	8.50	8.56	8.63	6.52	4.58

Activation parameters : The effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction was studied at four different temperatures (20, 25, 30 and 35°) and the data thus obtained are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE RATE CONSTANT, k_c

Temp. K	293	298	303	308
$k_c \times 10^4$, sec ⁻¹	2.69	3.96	6.71	8.74

The plot of log k_c vs $1/T$ was found to be a straight line showing that the reaction obeys Arrhenius temperature dependence. From this plot, the values of E_a , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger were determined and found to be 53.6 kJ mol⁻¹, -83.3 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, 56.1 kJ mol⁻¹ and 82.1 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Spectrophotometric evidence for the complexation of vanadium(V) with oxalic acid : Since the absorbance of vanadium(V) was found to increase with increase in [oxalic acid], it was suspected that there might be some complex formation between vanadium(V) and oxalic acid. Absorbances of solutions containing 0.001 M vanadium(V) and varying [oxalic acid] (upto 80 fold) in 1 M HClO_4 were measured at 280 nm, where the absorbance of the resultant solutions is maximum. When the reciprocals of the absorbance thus measured were plotted against the reciprocals of [oxalic acid] a straight line was obtained indicating the formation of a 1 : 1 complex. The stability constant of this complex has been calculated, adopting Ardon's procedure⁹, from the intercept and slope of this

plot and found to be equal to 21 mol⁻¹ lit. Further increase in [oxalic acid] caused a decrease in the absorbance, which may be due to the formation of a 1:2 complex as suggested by Jones and Waters¹⁰.

A perusal of literature shows that the preponderant species of vanadium(V)¹¹⁻¹⁸ in aqueous acid solution is VO₂⁺ and that of nitrous acid is the unionised HNO₂. Further, since the first dissociation constant of oxalic acid is 5.40 × 10⁻², it may be regarded as existing in the unionised form under the conditions employed in this investigation. In view of the kinetic and spectrophotometric evidences obtained for the formation of a 1:1 complex between vanadium(V) and oxalic acid, the catalytic effect of the latter may be attributed to the formation of this complex.

Mechanism :

where OX represents oxalic acid.

Applying steady state approximation to [C₂],

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 [\text{C}_1]_e [\text{VO}_2^+] [\text{HNO}_2]}{(k_2 [\text{NO}_2^-] + k_3 [\text{VO}_2^+]_e)} \quad \dots (4)$$

But, from equation (1)

$$[\text{VO}_2^+]_e = \frac{[\text{VO}_2^+]_t}{(1 + K[\text{OX}])} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and } [\text{C}_1]_e = \frac{K[\text{VO}_2^+][\text{OX}]}{(1 + K[\text{OX}])} \quad \dots (6)$$

Substituting for [VO₂⁺]_e and [C₁] from equations (5) and (6), in equation (4)

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 K [\text{VO}_2^+]_t^2 [\text{OX}] [\text{HNO}_2]}{(1 + K[\text{OX}]) + (k_3 [\text{NO}_2^-] + k_2 K [\text{NO}_2^-] [\text{OX}] + k_3 [\text{VO}_2^+]_t)} \quad \dots (7)$$

This rate equation predicts that the plot of 1/rate vs [NO₂⁻] should be a straight line with an intercept on the rate axis. When the data presented in Table 1 are plotted, exactly such a plot is obtained thus substantiating the proposed mechanism.

In the absence of added nitrate, equation (7) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{2k_1 K [\text{VO}_2^+]_t [\text{OX}] [\text{HNO}_2]}{(1 + K[\text{OX}])}$$

The above rate equation explains the observed first order in vanadium(V) and nitrous acid and fractional order in oxalic acid. Further, it also explains the absence of the effect of [H⁺] on the rate constant, which has been observed in the [H⁺] range of 0.5-1.2 M. The decrease in rate constant

with further increase in [H⁺] may be due to the dissociation of the kinetically active complex, as suggested by Jones and Waters¹⁰. From the rate, it is possible to calculate the values of K, k₁ and k₂/k₃. The formation constant K calculated in this way is found to be 16 mol⁻¹ lit, which is in reasonably good agreement with the spectrophotometrically obtained value of 21 mol⁻¹ lit. The values of k₁ and k₂/k₃ calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot of 1/k_o vs [NO₂⁻] are 9.43 × 10² mol⁻¹ lit sec⁻¹ and 9.68 × 10⁻², respectively.

The higher reactivity of vanadium(V)-oxalic acid complex compared to that of vanadium(V) may be due to the more favourable electron path which the former provides through the π electron system of the ligand.

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